

Photon count rates for the UBVRI, H-beta and Stromvil systems

L Lindegren 1997 July 22 (gaia_ll_7)

The expected photon counts rates (in Hz) have been calculated for several spectral types, including reddened ($A_V = 5$) stars. The stellar fluxes and optical parameters were the same as used in gaia_ll_5, assuming two circular pupils of 0.6 m diameter, optical transmittance 0.8, and quantum efficiency according to Table 1. On top of the system transmittance of 0.8, rectangular passbands were defined as in Table 2. NF stands for 'No Filter' and corresponds to the count rates in gaia_ll_5.

Resulting count rates (in Hz) are given in Table 3. They refer always to a star of magnitude $V = 15$. The calculated (Cousins') R and I magnitudes are given in columns 4 and 5. Note that the VRI magnitudes in columns 3-5 were calculated with the detailed (energy-weighted) response curves from Bessell, not from the approximate passbands in Table 2. This is why the count rate in the 'V' band varies with spectral type and reddening.

Table 1. The assumed quantum efficiency was obtained by linear interpolation of the following data points.

lambda	QE
300	0.00
320	0.22
350	0.50
375	0.58
400	0.72
450	0.85
500	0.85
600	0.84
700	0.78
750	0.69
800	0.50
900	0.28
1000	0.05
1050	0.00

Table 2. Central wavelength (Lambda0), width of the rectangular passband (FWHM) and maximum transmittance (Tmax) for each of the filters.

	NF	U	B	V	Rc	Ic	Bn	Bw	35	37	38	41	47	52	55	66	81
lambda0	700.00	366.00	445.00	550.00	645.00	800.00	486.00	486.00	350.00	374.00	383.00	411.00	467.00	516.00	547.00	656.00	812.00
FWHM	800.00	50.00	100.00	100.00	150.00	140.00	3.00	25.00	30.00	26.00	20.00	19.00	18.00	21.00	23.00	20.00	166.00
Tmax	1.00	.85	.88	.95	.72	.96	.70	.70	.40	.42	.50	.60	.70	.80	.80	.80	.90

Table 3. Calculated VRI magnitudes, and count rates (Hz) for the different filters

Sp	A.V	V	Rc	B	V	Rc	Ic	Bn	Bw	35	37	38	41	47	52	55	66	81		
B01b	.0	15.00	15.14	15.33	1933E+05	2597E+04	5522E+04	3639E+04	2630E+04	.1176E+04	1.054E+03	.9261E+03	.6915E+03	.6756E+03	.6506E+03	.6253E+03	.6055E+03	.7083E+03	.3631E+03	.1213E+04
B1V	.0	15.00	15.16	15.33	1909E+05	2414E+04	5684E+04	3604E+04	2591E+04	.1175E+04	1.047E+03	.9339E+03	.6314E+03	.6294E+03	.6253E+03	.6055E+03	.6055E+03	.7083E+03	.3631E+03	.1213E+04
A0V	.0	15.00	15.01	15.02	1650E+05	8829E+03	4762E+04	3707E+04	2988E+04	.1581E+04	1.704E+02	8348E+02	8348E+02	2609E+03	2549E+03	2549E+03	2549E+03	.7141E+03	.3969E+03	.1638E+04
A5V	.0	15.00	14.87	14.73	1647E+05	6620E+03	3929E+04	3769E+04	3424E+04	.2081E+04	7.444E+02	7853E+02	1.257E+03	1918E+03	1918E+03	1918E+03	1918E+03	.7069E+03	.7490E+03	.4731E+03
F6V	.0	15.00	14.75	14.49	1724E+05	6195E+03	3463E+04	3836E+04	3894E+04	.2624E+04	7.904E+02	7521E+02	1.291E+03	1766E+03	1766E+03	1766E+03	1766E+03	.6785E+03	.7517E+03	.5470E+03
G2V	.0	15.00	14.65	14.30	1783E+05	4780E+03	2996E+04	3889E+04	4293E+04	.3149E+04	8.080E+02	7191E+02	1.032E+03	1358E+03	1358E+03	1358E+03	1358E+03	.6648E+03	.7586E+03	.6353E+03
G8III	.0	15.00	14.49	14.04	1890E+05	1953E+03	2350E+04	3894E+04	4067E+04	.4003E+04	7.255E+02	6517E+02	3.063E+02	5780E+02	5540E+02	5540E+02	5540E+02	.6319E+03	.7780E+03	.7360E+03
K3V	.0	15.00	14.46	14.02	1930E+05	2075E+03	2421E+04	4023E+04	4937E+04	.4088E+04	7.664E+02	6571E+02	3.455E+02	5981E+02	5464E+02	5464E+02	5464E+02	.5857E+03	.7935E+03	.7757E+03
K3III	.0	15.00	14.28	13.67	2237E+05	1779E+04	4177E+04	4023E+04	5137E+04	.5706E+04	6.585E+02	5735E+02	1.352E+02	2310E+02	2168E+02	2168E+02	2168E+02	.5611E+03	.7902E+03	.9397E+03
M0V	.0	15.00	14.07	13.26	2803E+05	9250E+02	1757E+04	4258E+04	7337E+04	.8369E+04	6.415E+02	5252E+02	1.943E+02	2650E+02	2729E+02	2729E+02	2729E+02	.4663E+03	.8462E+03	.1204E+04
M0III	.0	15.00	14.12	13.30	2727E+05	4267E+02	1504E+04	4199E+04	6999E+04	.8196E+04	5.784E+02	4508E+02	1.758E+01	1293E+02	1297E+02	1297E+02	1297E+02	.5060E+03	.8332E+03	.1112E+04
M8V	.0	15.00	13.63	11.86	7189E+05	5636E+02	1198E+04	4095E+04	9335E+04	.3229E+05	4.891E+02	4.194E+02	1.185E+02	1771E+02	1860E+02	1860E+02	1860E+02	.5267E+03	.8581E+03	.1955E+04
M7III	.0	15.00	12.77	10.46	2870E+06	1264E+03	1.176E+04	4.037E+04	1.669E+05	.1189E+06	2.526E+02	2.784E+02	1.113E+02	.4343E+02	.5535E+02	.5535E+02	.5535E+02	.5460E+03	.8397E+03	.3130E+04
B01b	5.0	15.00	14.17	13.35	2737E+05	2530E+03	1.613E+04	4.207E+04	6.731E+04	.7821E+04	5.098E+02	4.491E+02	5.124E+02	.7296E+02	.8017E+02	.8017E+02	.8017E+02	.5666E+03	.8202E+03	.1042E+04
B1V	5.0	15.00	14.17	13.34	2715E+05	2382E+03	1.675E+04	4.172E+04	6.734E+04	.7807E+04	5.115E+02	4.576E+02	4.715E+02	.6890E+02	.7777E+02	.7777E+02	.7777E+02	.5672E+03	.8070E+03	.1058E+04
A0V	5.0	15.00	14.03	13.06	3262E+05	9218E+02	1.393E+04	4.255E+04	7.648E+04	.1029E+05	3.348E+02	3.987E+02	1.109E+02	.2886E+02	.4365E+02	.4365E+02	.4365E+02	.5477E+03	.8124E+03	.1119E+04
A5V	5.0	15.00	13.88	12.78	3923E+05	6633E+02	1.167E+04	4.303E+04	8.767E+04	.1340E+05	3.470E+02	3.682E+02	9.082E+01	.2053E+02	.2821E+02	.2821E+02	.2821E+02	.4889E+03	.8384E+03	.1310E+04
F6V	5.0	15.00	13.74	12.55	4586E+05	5974E+02	1.031E+04	4.357E+04	9.908E+04	.1661E+05	3.620E+02	3.465E+02	9.168E+01	.1831E+02	.2227E+02	.2227E+02	.2227E+02	.4889E+03	.8264E+03	.1487E+04
G2V	5.0	15.00	13.64	12.38	5257E+05	4474E+02	8996E+03	4.383E+04	1.082E+05	.1958E+05	3.630E+02	3.254E+02	7.196E+01	.1370E+02	.1597E+02	.1597E+02	.1597E+02	.4703E+03	.8192E+03	.1696E+04
G8III	5.0	15.00	13.50	12.15	6358E+05	1778E+02	7183E+03	4.458E+04	1.226E+05	2.433E+05	3.172E+02	2.911E+01	2.701E+01	.5572E+01	.6195E+01	.6195E+01	.6195E+01	.4284E+03	.8177E+03	.1911E+04
K3V	5.0	15.00	13.28	11.61	8558E+05	1848E+02	7334E+03	4.495E+04	1.489E+05	3.270E+05	3.319E+02	2.911E+01	3.077E+01	.5699E+01	.6049E+01	.6049E+01	.6049E+01	.4006E+03	.8289E+03	.1995E+04
K3III	5.0	15.00	13.28	11.61	8558E+05	6827E+01	5517E+03	4.547E+04	1.489E+05	3.270E+05	3.319E+02	2.911E+01	3.077E+01	.5699E+01	.6049E+01	.6049E+01	.6049E+01	.3733E+03	.8075E+03	.2353E+04
M0V	5.0	15.00	13.08	11.45	1133E+06	7774E+01	5180E+03	4.621E+04	1.722E+05	4.733E+05	2.581E+02	2.141E+01	1.126E+01	.2401E+01	.2812E+01	.2812E+01	.2812E+01	.2988E+03	.8211E+03	.2880E+04
M0III	5.0	15.00	13.11	11.46	1161E+06	3704E+01	4653E+03	4.578E+04	1.678E+05	4.740E+05	2.371E+02	2.124E+01	1.183E+01	.1183E+01	.1365E+01	.1365E+01	.1365E+01	.3281E+03	.8215E+03	.2708E+04
M8V	5.0	15.00	12.36	9.99	4452E+06	4870E+01	5763E+03	4.376E+04	2.389E+05	1.924E+06	2.006E+02	1.756E+01	7.481E+00	.1646E+01	.1963E+01	.1963E+01	.1963E+01	.3423E+03	.8360E+03	.4747E+04
M7III	5.0	15.00	11.38	8.63	2091E+07	1.108E+02	.2896E+03	.4055E+04	.4220E+05	.6702E+06	.9631E+01	.1100E+03	.7039E+00	.3799E+01	.5413E+01	.5413E+01	.5413E+01	.3227E+03	.7632E+03	.7052E+04

Addendum to gaia_ll_7:

Table 3 was used to compute the V, Rc and Ic magnitudes at which a given spectral type gives a count rate of 100 Hz in the different filters. Results are given in Tables 4 to 6 below. They give a rough idea of the limiting magnitudes for the photometric measurements. The column for NF ('no filter') corresponds to the magnitudes in gaia_ll_5.

Table 4. V-magnitudes giving a count rate of 100 Hz with different filters

Sp	A_V	NF	U	B	V	Rc	Ic	Bn	Bw	35	37	38	41	47	52	55	66	81
B0Ib	0	20.7	18.5	19.4	18.9	18.5	17.7	15.1	17.4	17.1	17.1	17.0	17.2	17.2	17.2	17.1	16.4	17.7
B1V	0	20.7	18.5	19.4	18.9	18.5	17.7	15.0	17.4	17.0	17.0	17.0	17.3	17.2	17.2	17.1	16.4	17.7
A0V	0	20.5	17.4	19.2	18.9	18.7	18.0	14.6	17.3	15.5	16.0	16.4	17.0	17.1	17.2	17.1	16.5	18.0
A5V	0	20.5	17.1	19.0	18.9	18.8	18.3	14.7	17.2	15.2	15.7	15.9	16.7	17.0	17.1	17.2	16.7	18.3
F6V	0	20.6	17.0	18.8	19.0	19.0	18.5	14.7	17.2	15.3	15.6	15.7	16.5	16.9	17.1	17.2	16.8	18.6
G2V	0	20.6	16.7	18.7	19.0	19.1	18.7	14.8	17.1	15.0	15.3	15.4	16.3	16.7	17.1	17.2	17.0	18.8
G8III	0	20.7	15.7	18.4	19.0	19.2	19.0	14.7	17.0	14.0	14.4	14.4	15.7	16.6	17.0	17.2	17.2	19.1
K3V	0	20.7	15.8	18.5	19.0	19.3	19.0	14.7	17.1	14.1	14.4	14.3	15.7	16.6	16.9	17.3	17.2	19.1
K3III	0	20.9	14.7	18.1	19.0	19.5	19.4	14.5	16.9	13.0	13.4	13.3	15.0	16.4	16.9	17.3	17.4	19.5
M0V	0	21.1	14.9	18.1	19.1	19.7	19.8	14.5	16.8	13.2	13.6	13.6	15.1	16.5	16.7	17.3	17.7	19.9
M0III	0	21.1	14.1	17.9	19.1	19.6	19.8	14.4	16.8	12.2	12.8	12.8	14.6	16.3	16.8	17.3	17.6	19.9
M8V	0	22.1	14.4	17.7	19.0	19.9	21.3	14.2	16.6	12.7	13.1	13.2	14.4	16.1	16.8	17.3	18.2	21.4
M7III	0	23.6	15.3	17.7	19.0	20.6	22.7	13.5	16.1	12.6	14.1	14.4	15.8	15.3	16.8	17.3	18.7	22.9
B0Ib	5	21.1	16.0	18.0	19.1	19.6	19.7	14.3	16.6	14.3	14.7	14.8	15.4	16.1	16.9	17.3	17.5	19.8
B1V	5	21.1	15.9	18.1	19.1	19.6	19.7	14.3	16.7	14.2	14.6	14.7	15.4	16.1	16.9	17.3	17.6	19.8
A0V	5	21.3	14.9	17.9	19.1	19.7	20.0	13.8	16.5	12.6	13.7	14.1	15.2	16.0	16.8	17.3	17.6	20.1
A5V	5	21.5	14.6	17.7	19.1	19.9	20.3	13.9	16.4	12.4	13.3	13.6	14.8	15.9	16.8	17.3	17.8	20.4
F6V	5	21.7	14.4	17.5	19.1	20.0	20.6	13.9	16.3	12.4	13.2	13.4	14.6	15.7	16.7	17.3	17.9	20.6
G2V	5	21.8	14.1	17.4	19.1	20.1	20.7	13.9	16.3	12.1	12.8	13.0	14.3	15.6	16.7	17.3	18.1	20.8
G8III	5	22.0	13.1	17.1	19.1	20.2	21.0	13.8	16.1	11.1	11.9	12.0	13.7	15.4	16.6	17.3	18.2	21.1
K3V	5	22.0	13.2	17.2	19.1	20.3	21.0	13.8	16.2	11.2	11.9	12.0	13.8	15.4	16.5	17.3	18.2	21.1
K3III	5	22.3	12.1	16.9	19.1	20.4	21.3	13.6	16.0	10.0	10.8	10.9	13.0	15.2	16.4	17.3	18.4	21.4
M0V	5	22.6	12.2	16.8	19.2	20.6	21.7	13.5	15.8	10.2	11.0	11.1	13.0	15.2	16.2	17.3	18.6	21.8
M0III	5	22.7	11.4	16.7	19.2	20.6	21.7	13.4	15.8	9.3	10.2	10.3	12.6	15.1	16.3	17.3	18.6	21.8
M8V	5	24.1	11.7	16.4	19.1	20.9	23.2	13.3	15.6	9.7	10.5	10.7	12.3	14.9	16.3	17.3	19.2	23.4
M7III	5	25.8	12.6	16.2	19.0	21.6	24.6	12.5	15.1	9.6	11.4	11.8	13.7	14.0	16.3	17.2	19.6	24.8

Table 5. Rc-magnitudes giving a count rate of 100 Hz with different filters

Sp	A_V	NF	U	B	V	Rc	Ic	Bn	Bw	35	37	38	41	47	52	55	66	81
B0Ib	0	20.9	18.7	19.5	19.0	18.7	17.8	15.2	17.6	17.2	17.2	17.2	17.4	17.3	17.3	17.3	16.5	17.8
B1V	0	20.9	18.6	19.5	19.1	18.7	17.8	15.2	17.6	17.2	17.2	17.2	17.4	17.4	17.4	17.3	16.6	17.9
A0V	0	20.6	17.4	19.2	18.9	18.7	18.0	14.6	17.3	15.5	16.1	16.4	17.0	17.1	17.2	17.1	16.5	18.0
A5V	0	20.4	16.9	18.9	18.8	18.7	18.2	14.5	17.1	15.1	15.6	15.8	16.6	16.8	17.0	17.1	16.6	18.2
F6V	0	20.3	16.7	18.6	18.7	18.7	18.3	14.5	16.9	15.0	15.4	15.4	16.2	16.6	16.8	16.9	16.6	18.3
G2V	0	20.3	16.3	18.3	18.6	18.7	18.4	14.4	16.8	14.7	15.0	15.0	15.9	16.4	16.7	16.9	16.7	18.4
G8III	0	20.2	15.2	17.9	18.5	18.7	18.5	14.1	16.5	13.5	13.9	13.8	15.2	16.1	16.5	16.7	16.7	18.5
K3V	0	20.2	15.3	17.9	18.5	18.7	18.5	14.2	16.5	13.6	13.9	13.8	15.2	16.1	16.4	16.7	16.7	18.5
K3III	0	20.2	14.0	17.4	18.3	18.7	18.7	13.8	16.2	12.3	12.7	12.6	14.3	15.7	16.2	16.5	16.7	18.7
M0V	0	20.2	14.0	17.2	18.1	18.7	18.9	13.6	15.9	12.3	12.6	12.7	14.1	15.6	15.7	16.4	16.8	18.9
M0III	0	20.2	13.2	17.1	18.2	18.7	18.9	13.5	15.9	11.3	11.9	11.9	13.7	15.4	15.9	16.4	16.7	19.0
M8V	0	20.8	13.0	16.3	17.7	18.6	19.9	12.9	15.2	11.3	11.8	11.8	13.0	14.7	15.4	16.0	16.9	20.0
M7III	0	21.4	13.0	15.4	16.8	18.3	20.5	11.3	13.9	10.4	11.9	12.1	13.6	13.1	14.6	15.1	16.5	20.6
B0Ib	5	20.3	15.2	17.2	18.2	18.7	18.9	13.4	15.8	13.4	13.8	13.9	14.5	15.3	16.1	16.5	16.7	19.0
B1V	5	20.3	15.1	17.2	18.2	18.7	18.9	13.4	15.8	13.4	13.8	13.9	14.6	15.3	16.1	16.4	16.7	19.0
A0V	5	20.3	13.9	16.9	18.1	18.7	19.1	12.8	15.5	11.6	12.7	13.1	14.2	15.0	15.9	16.3	16.7	19.1
A5V	5	20.4	13.4	16.5	18.0	18.7	19.2	12.7	15.3	11.3	12.2	12.5	13.7	14.7	15.7	16.2	16.7	19.3
F6V	5	20.4	13.2	16.3	17.8	18.7	19.3	12.6	15.1	11.1	11.9	12.1	13.3	14.5	15.5	16.0	16.7	19.4
G2V	5	20.4	12.8	16.0	17.7	18.7	19.4	12.5	14.9	10.8	11.5	11.6	13.0	14.2	15.3	15.9	16.7	19.5
G8III	5	20.5	11.6	15.6	17.6	18.7	19.5	12.3	14.6	9.6	10.4	10.5	12.2	13.9	15.1	15.8	16.7	19.6
K3V	5	20.5	11.6	15.6	17.6	18.7	19.5	12.3	14.6	9.7	10.4	10.4	12.2	13.9	15.0	15.8	16.7	19.5
K3III	5	20.6	10.4	15.1	17.4	18.7	19.6	11.9	14.3	8.3	9.1	9.2	11.3	13.5	14.7	15.5	16.7	19.7
M0V	5	20.7	10.3	14.9	17.2	18.7	19.8	11.6	13.9	8.3	9.0	9.2	11.1	13.3	14.3	15.4	16.7	19.9
M0III	5	20.8	9.5	14.8	17.3	18.7	19.8	11.5	13.9	7.4	8.3	8.4	10.7	13.2	14.4	15.4	16.7	19.9
M8V	5	21.5	9.1	13.8	16.5	18.3	20.6	10.6	13.0	7.0	7.9	8.1	9.7	12.2	13.7	14.7	16.6	20.7
M7III	5	22.2	9.0	12.5	15.4	17.9	20.9	8.8	11.5	6.0	7.8	8.2	10.1	10.4	12.7	13.6	16.0	21.2

Table 6. Ic-magnitudes giving a count rate of 100 Hz with different filters

Sp	A_V	NF	U	B	V	Rc	Ic	Bn	Bw	35	37	38	41	47	52	55	66	81
B0Ib	0	21.0	18.9	19.7	19.2	18.9	18.0	15.4	17.7	17.4	17.4	17.4	17.6	17.5	17.5	17.5	16.7	18.0
B1V	0	21.0	18.8	19.7	19.2	18.9	18.0	15.4	17.8	17.3	17.3	17.3	17.6	17.5	17.5	17.4	16.7	18.0
A0V	0	20.6	17.4	19.2	18.9	18.7	18.0	14.6	17.3	15.5	16.1	16.4	17.0	17.1	17.2	17.2	16.5	18.1
A5V	0	20.3	16.8	18.7	18.7	18.6	18.0	14.4	17.0	15.0	15.4	15.7	16.4	16.7	16.9	16.9	16.4	18.1

F6V	0	20.1	16.5	18.3	18.4	18.5	18.0	14.2	16.7	14.8	15.1	15.2	16.0	16.3	16.6	16.7	16.3	18.1
G2V	0	19.9	16.0	18.0	18.3	18.4	18.0	14.1	16.4	14.3	14.6	14.7	15.6	16.0	16.4	16.5	16.3	18.1
G8III	0	19.7	14.8	17.5	18.0	18.3	18.0	13.7	16.1	13.0	13.4	13.4	14.7	15.6	16.0	16.3	16.2	18.1
K3V	0	19.7	14.8	17.5	18.0	18.3	18.0	13.7	16.1	13.2	13.5	13.4	14.8	15.6	15.9	16.3	16.2	18.1
K3III	0	19.5	13.4	16.8	17.7	18.1	18.1	13.2	15.6	11.6	12.1	12.0	13.7	15.1	15.5	15.9	16.1	18.1
M0V	0	19.4	13.2	16.4	17.3	17.9	18.1	12.8	15.1	11.5	11.8	11.9	13.3	14.7	14.9	15.6	16.0	18.1
M0III	0	19.4	12.4	16.2	17.4	17.9	18.1	12.7	15.1	10.5	11.1	11.1	12.9	14.6	15.1	15.6	15.9	18.2
M8V	0	19.0	11.2	14.6	15.9	16.8	18.1	11.1	13.4	9.5	10.0	10.0	11.2	13.0	13.7	14.2	15.1	18.2
M7III	0	19.1	10.7	13.1	14.5	16.0	18.1	9.0	11.6	8.1	9.6	9.8	11.2	10.8	12.3	12.8	14.2	18.3
B0Ib	5	19.4	14.4	16.4	17.4	17.9	18.1	12.6	15.0	12.6	13.0	13.1	13.7	14.4	15.2	15.6	15.9	18.2
B1V	5	19.4	14.3	16.4	17.4	17.9	18.1	12.6	15.0	12.5	12.9	13.1	13.8	14.5	15.3	15.6	15.9	18.1
A0V	5	19.3	13.0	15.9	17.1	17.8	18.1	11.9	14.6	10.7	11.7	12.2	13.2	14.1	14.9	15.3	15.7	18.2
A5V	5	19.3	12.3	15.4	16.9	17.6	18.1	11.6	14.2	10.2	11.1	11.4	12.6	13.6	14.6	15.1	15.6	18.2
F6V	5	19.2	12.0	15.1	16.6	17.5	18.1	11.4	13.9	10.0	10.7	10.9	12.1	13.3	14.3	14.8	15.5	18.2
G2V	5	19.2	11.5	14.8	16.5	17.5	18.1	11.3	13.7	9.5	10.2	10.4	11.7	13.0	14.1	14.7	15.5	18.2
G8III	5	19.2	10.3	14.3	16.3	17.4	18.1	10.9	13.3	8.2	9.0	9.1	10.9	12.6	13.7	14.4	15.4	18.2
K3V	5	19.2	10.3	14.3	16.3	17.4	18.1	10.9	13.3	8.4	9.0	9.1	10.9	12.6	13.6	14.4	15.4	18.2
K3III	5	19.1	8.9	13.7	16.0	17.2	18.1	10.4	12.8	6.8	7.6	7.7	9.8	12.0	13.2	14.1	15.2	18.2
M0V	5	19.1	8.7	13.2	15.6	17.0	18.1	10.0	12.3	6.7	7.4	7.6	9.5	11.7	12.6	13.7	15.1	18.2
M0III	5	19.1	7.9	13.1	15.6	17.0	18.1	9.9	12.3	5.7	6.6	6.8	9.0	11.5	12.8	13.7	15.0	18.3
M8V	5	19.1	6.7	11.4	14.1	15.9	18.2	8.2	10.6	4.7	5.5	5.7	7.3	9.8	11.3	12.3	14.2	18.4
M7III	5	19.4	6.2	9.8	12.6	15.2	18.2	6.1	8.7	3.2	5.1	5.5	7.3	7.7	9.9	10.8	13.3	18.5